

THE EXPRESSION OF AXIOLOGICAL LEXICAL UNITS IN LANGUAGE

Dadabayeva Shirinxon Shuxratovna

PhD in Philological Sciences, Associate Professor,
Fergana State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15396369>

Abstract. This article is devoted to the study of axiological lexicon – the expression of values in language. The study analyzes the semantic and stylistic features of lexical units, as well as the implicit and explicit evaluation processes, highlighting their role in reflecting the values and norms of society. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the conceptual model of value expression in language.

Keywords: *Axiology, Axiolinguistics, Evaluation Process, Ranking Process, Semantic Meaning, Evaluation Theory, Implicit Evaluation, Explicit Evaluation.*

Axiological Lexicon is a subfield of axiolinguistics that studies the layer of language composed of words and expressions which convey values and evaluations, both implicitly and explicitly. This layer includes:

- Evaluative adjectives (e.g., *good, bad*);
- Evaluative adverbs (e.g., *unfortunately*);
- Nouns expressing dignity and worth (e.g., *freedom, honor*);
- Interjections (e.g., *please!, bless you!, oh my!*);
- Idiomatic expressions (e.g., *dark days*);
- Proverbs.

According to many scholars, axiological lexicon is seen as a central component of social relations. This is because words are the primary linguistic units that express the values and norms of a society, making them the main object of study in axiology.

The term “axiologeme” was first introduced by K.A. Zhukov, who used it to describe a layer of vocabulary with evaluative meaning. He emphasized the linguistic relevance of such words and noted that they can carry both positive and negative meanings [6].

In addition to “axiological lexicon,” several other related terms are found in both English and Uzbek linguistic literature:

- Evaluative lexicon – used primarily in appraisal theory, examining how language conveys judgments and evaluations. This term was used by J.R. Martin and P.R. White [4].

- Value-laden vocabulary – typically found in discourse analysis, referring to words with distinctive ideological or connotative evaluative meanings [1]. In

Uzbek linguistics, this term has also been used to denote value-related lexical units [2].

- Evaluative language – a broader term encompassing not just words but other linguistic elements conveying evaluation [3].

- Moral terminology (moral lexicon) – used for lexical units that reflect social norms [2].

- Forms of subjective evaluation – a term introduced by R. Qo'ng'irov, who analyzes the semantic and stylistic features of such elements and their expression in speech [5].

Conclusion. Thus, even though many researchers do not explicitly use the term “axiological lexicon,” it is evident that the units or forms they study fall precisely within this category.

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